

1 Biotrickling filter modeling for styrene abatement. Part 2:

2 Simulating a two-phase partitioning bioreactor

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18

19 **Abstract**

20 A dynamic model describing styrene abatement was developed for a two-phase partitioning
21 bioreactor operated as a biotrickling filter (TPPB-BTF). The model was built as a coupled set
22 of two different systems of partial differential equations depending on whether an irrigation
23 or a non-irrigation period was simulated. The maximum growth rate was previously
24 calibrated from a conventional BTF treating styrene (Part 1). The model was extended to
25 simulate the TPPB-BTF based on the hypothesis that the main change associated with the
26 non-aqueous phase is the modification of the pollutant properties in the liquid phase. The
27 three phases considered were gas, a water–silicone liquid mixture, and biofilm. The selected
28 calibration parameters were related to the physical properties of styrene: Henry’s law
29 constant, diffusivity, and the gas–liquid mass transfer coefficient. A sensitivity analysis
30 revealed that Henry’s law constant was the most sensitive parameter. The model was
31 successfully calibrated with a goodness of fit of 0.94. It satisfactorily simulated the
32 performance of the TPPB-BTF at styrene loads ranging from 13 to 77 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹ and empty
33 bed residence times of 30–15 s with the mass transfer enhanced by a factor of 1.6. The model
34 was validated with data obtained in a TPPB-BTF removing styrene continuously. The
35 experimental outlet emissions associated to oscillating inlet concentrations were satisfactorily
36 predicted by using the calibrated parameters. Model simulations demonstrated the potential
37 improvement of the mass-transfer performance of a conventional BTF degrading styrene by
38 adding silicone oil.

39

40 **Keywords:** Biological air treatment; Biotrickling filter; Mathematical modeling; Silicone oil;
41 Styrene; Two-phase partitioning bioreactor

42

43 **1. Introduction**

44 One of the main limitations of the abatement of styrene-laden air streams by biotechnological
45 processes is the poor aqueous solubility of the compound and its toxicity to microbial
46 communities (Dumont et al., 2014). Therefore, two-phase partitioning bioreactors (TPPBs),
47 which are biological systems provided with a non-aqueous phase (NAP) with a high affinity
48 for target pollutants, have been reported as a feasible treatment technology for compounds
49 such as styrene (Muñoz et al., 2012; Rene et al., 2011; San-Valero et al., 2017). The styrene-
50 removal enhancement in TPPBs is attributed to the high solubility of styrene in silicone oil,
51 which is approximately 236 times higher than that in water (Patel et al., 2017). The NAP
52 addition can also buffer volatile organic compound (VOC)-loading surges and avoid
53 starvation periods by acting as a pollutant reservoir (Bailón et al., 2009). Several studies have
54 demonstrated that most NAPs also show a high affinity toward oxygen; consequently, the
55 oxygen mass transfer rate might also be improved in TPPBs (Daugulis et al., 2011;
56 Kraakman et al., 2011; Quijano et al., 2009b).

57 Several experimental studies on VOC removal in TPPBs have focused on the quantification
58 of mass transport coefficients (Dumont and Andrès, 2012; Hernández et al., 2011;
59 Moradkhani et al., 2017) and on the process microbiology (Darracq et al., 2012; Karimi et al.,
60 2013; Ordaz et al., 2014). However, these aspects have not been incorporated in a
61 comprehensive mathematical description of TPPBs operated as biotrickling filters (TPPB-
62 BTFs).

63 TPPB-BTFs present the same reactor configuration as that found in conventional BTFs;
64 however, the recirculated aqueous solution is provided with the NAP. Although studies on
65 TPPB-BTFs treating styrene are scarce in the literature (Zamir et al., 2015), compounds with
66 a similar solubility (e.g., VOCs with dimensionless Henry's law constants between 0.1 and
67 1.0 at 25°C and 1atm), such as dichloromethane or α -pinene, have been abated satisfactorily

68 in TPPB-BTFs using silicone oil as the NAP (Bailón et al., 2009; Muñoz et al., 2008). In a
69 previous study in our laboratory, we demonstrated that that a TPPB-BTF using industrial-
70 grade silicone oil removed styrene with higher efficiency and stability than a conventional
71 BTF operated under the same conditions (San-Valero et al., 2017). In this study, the removal
72 efficiency (RE) obtained was approximately 40% higher than that of the conventional BTF
73 without an NAP, while supporting a critical inlet load (IL) two times higher than in the
74 conventional BTF.

75 Studies on TPPB-BTF modeling are limited. Parnian et al. (2016) proposed an approach for
76 styrene mass transfer estimation in a BTF with silicone oil from a modeling framework based
77 on general mass balances and transfer equations described by Hernández et al. (2011).

78 Dorado et al. (2015) proposed a novel mathematical description of TPPBs from experimental
79 findings reported in stirred tanks. A comprehensive description of the complex mass transfer
80 phenomena occurring simultaneously in TPPBs was conducted using the partial mass transfer
81 coefficients for both VOCs and oxygen in stirred tanks.

82 TPPB-BTFs are complex multiphase systems that represent a challenge from a mathematical
83 modeling point of view. The occurrence of simultaneous transfer pathways for both VOCs
84 and oxygen makes the experimental determination of individual mass transfer coefficients
85 difficult (Muñoz et al., 2012). On the other hand, most BTF models available in the literature
86 do not consider intermittent irrigation, which is a common practice in industrial BTFs
87 (Sempere et al., 2012). Intermittent irrigation strongly affects the BTF performance;
88 therefore, it must be considered in the mathematical description (San-Valero et al., 2015).

89 Unfortunately, no systematical studies on styrene removal in TPPB-BTFs considering such
90 industrial operating conditions are available in the literature.

91 In this work, a dynamic model for simulating the performance of a TPPB-BTF was assessed
92 by adapting the model developed for a styrene-degrading BTF without a NAP addition,

93 which was presented Part 1. The calibration and validation of the model were conducted
94 using the experimental data from a TPPB-BTF treating styrene using silicone oil as the NAP.
95 The results obtained from the multiphase system were compared with those obtained in a
96 conventional BTF to quantify the potential benefits of adding silicone oil. The
97 phenomenological mathematical model developed in this study aimed to provide a better
98 understanding of the fundamental mechanisms that occur in this bioprocess, so that the
99 critical design and operational parameters could be identified.

100

101 **2. Materials and methods**

102 2.1. Lab-scale plant operation for the TPPB

103 A lab-scale BTF identical to that in Part 1 was used (0.144 m inner diameter, 1.63 m height,
104 working volume of 20 L, working height = 1.23 m) with an external recirculation tank of 6 L.
105 The BTF was packed with polypropylene rings (25 mm nominal diameter, $a = 207 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-3}$, θ_P
106 = 92%). The liquid phase was intermittently irrigated (15 min every 2 h) with a liquid flow of
107 2.7 L min^{-1} . On day 0, 1 L of industrial-grade silicone oil (XIAMETER PMX-200, Univar,
108 Spain) containing culture sludge acclimated to styrene was added to the recirculation tank.
109 The silicone oil percentage was 5% v/v relative to the BTF packed volume. The kinematic
110 viscosity and the density of the silicone oil were 50 cSt and 0.96 g mL^{-1} , respectively. The
111 selected conditions for calibration purposes that corresponded to the average data
112 representing the stable conditions of the TPPB-BTF performance are presented in Table 1.
113 The inlet load (IL) was increased from $22 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ up to $43 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ by decreasing the
114 empty bed residence time (EBRT) from 30 to 15 s. Subsequently, the EBRT was maintained
115 at 15 s and the inlet concentration was increased, resulting in ILs from $13 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ to 77 g
116 $\text{C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$. The resilience of the TPPB-BTF was evaluated by the application of styrene shock
117 loadings under transient conditions with inlet concentrations varying from 100–700 mg C m^{-3}

118 ³. The purge of water (3 L) was carried out once per week, and it represented less than 4% of
119 the carbon fed to the reactor during the week. Further details can be found in San-Valero et
120 al. (2017).

121

122 Table 1. Experimental elimination capacity (EC) data (\pm standard deviation) used for the
123 calibration of the TPPB-BTF model (San-Valero et al., 2017)

Days	IL (g C m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)	Inlet conc. (mg C m ⁻³)	EBRT (s)	EC (g C m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)
20-36	22	184	30	19.0 \pm 1.0
38-47	33	184	20	27.1 \pm 1.7
50-60	43	181	15	30.8 \pm 2.6
62-67	23	98	15	19.1 \pm 1.1
68-70	77	323	15	43.2 \pm 1.5
71-75	13	55	15	11.7 \pm 0.0

124

125 2.2. Model assumptions in the TPPB

126 The dynamic model describing the styrene abatement was extended for a TPPB-BTF based
127 on the previous application of the model to simulate a conventional BTF treating styrene (see
128 Part 1). The model accounted for simulating discontinuous irrigation. At periods without
129 irrigation, the liquid phase was assumed to be a stagnant phase, and the convective transport
130 was excluded in the modeling. One of the most accepted assumptions of TPPB in continuous
131 stirred tank reactors' (CSTR) and aerated tanks' configuration is that the mass transfer
132 between water and a NAP is faster than that between gas and liquid phases; therefore, a
133 water–NAP equilibrium is considered (Dumont and Andrès, 2012; Quijano et al., 2010). This
134 assumption has also been used to represent the gas–liquid mass transfer phenomena in TPPB-
135 BTFs (Hernández et al., 2011; Parnian et al., 2016) and in TPPB-bioscrubbers (Yeom et al.,
136 2010). To extend the model, it was assumed that the hydrodynamics of the BTF are of good
137 mixing, allowing the liquid phase to be considered a pseudo-homogenous mixture of water
138 and silicone. The other key assumptions are based on the previous work of Dorado et al.

139 (2015) on the modeling of TPPB-CSTR: (1) the microbial kinetic parameters were assumed
 140 to remain the same as the conventional BTF treating styrene ($\mu_{\max} = 2.65 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $Y_{\text{sty}} =$
 141 0.33 , $Y_o = 0.12$, $K_{\text{sty}} = 0.154 \text{ g m}^{-3}$, $K_o = 0.26 \text{ g m}^{-3}$, Part 1); (2) based on the fact that silicone
 142 oil is approximately 50 times more affine for styrene than for oxygen, it was considered that
 143 the effect of the NAP on the oxygen mass transfer was negligible compared with that on the
 144 styrene mass transfer. Thus, the same parameters as for oxygen in Part 1 were used ($H_o =$
 145 31.4 , $D_o = 2.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $K_{La_o} = 0.013 \text{ s}^{-1}$, Part 1). Accordingly, the model was based on
 146 the hypothesis that the main change in the system performance associated with the addition
 147 of a NAP is the modification of the properties of the pollutant in the mixed water–silicone
 148 phase. According to these assumptions, the model equations for styrene were modified as
 149 follows:

150 Mass balance in the gas phase

$$151 \quad \theta_G \frac{\partial C_{G_{\text{sty}}}}{\partial t} = -v_G \frac{\partial C_{G_{\text{sty}}}}{\partial z} - K_L a_{\text{mix}} \left(\frac{C_{G_{\text{sty}}}}{H_{\text{mix}}} - C_{L_{\text{sty}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

152 Mass balance in the water–silicone liquid mixture

$$153 \quad \theta_L \frac{\partial C_{L_{\text{sty}}}}{\partial t} = v_L \frac{\partial C_{L_{\text{sty}}}}{\partial z} + K_L a_{\text{mix}} \left(\frac{C_{G_{\text{sty}}}}{H_{\text{mix}}} - C_{L_{\text{sty}}} \right) - \frac{D_{\text{mix}} a}{\beta} (C_{L_{\text{sty}}} - S_{\text{sty},1}) \quad (2)$$

154 Mass balance on the biofilm

$$155 \quad \frac{\partial S_{\text{sty}}}{\partial t} = f(X_v) D_{\text{mix}} \frac{\partial^2 S_{\text{sty}}}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\mu_{\max} X_v}{Y_{\text{sty}}} \frac{S_{\text{sty}}}{S_{\text{sty}} + K_{\text{sty}}} \frac{S_o}{S_o + K_o} \quad (3)$$

156

157 2.3. Model calibration and validation

158 Model calibration was performed by fitting the experimental data and model results
 159 corresponding to the steady state of the TPPB-BTF performance. The calibration parameters
 160 selected were related to the physical properties of styrene: the partition coefficient between
 161 gas and the liquid water–silicone mixture (H_{mix}), diffusivity (D_{mix}), and the gas–liquid mass

162 transfer coefficient ($K_{L,mix}$). The remaining parameters were kept the same as those in the
163 styrene-degrading BTF without a NAP ($\delta = 60 \times 10^{-6}$ m, $\beta = 3.8 \times 10^{-6}$ m, $X_v = 50$ kg m⁻³,
164 $f(X_v)=0.35$, $\theta_L=0.093$, $\theta_B =0.18$, Part1).

165 The mathematical procedure for calibration was similar to that described in Part 1, consisting
166 of the minimization of an objective function defined as the sum of the norm between the
167 experimental and the modeled RE using the algorithm *fminsearch* from MATLAB®. A
168 sensitivity analysis of the calibration parameters was conducted to evaluate their influence on
169 the model predictions. The validation of the model was conducted using the data on the
170 continuous monitoring of the TPPB-BTF under variable styrene inlet loadings, which are
171 operating conditions commonly found in industrial emissions.

172

173 **3. Results and discussion**

174 3.1. Model calibration

175 Model calibration was performed using the data from a TPPB treating styrene at several ILs
176 and EBRTs (San-Valero et al., 2017). The experimental conditions and elimination capacities
177 used for calibration are summarized in Table 1. The results corresponded to the average data
178 from the steady state elimination capacities (ECs) achieved at the end of each experimental
179 period. The calibration procedure resulted in the following apparent parameters: $K_{L,mix}$ of 9.2
180 $\times 10^{-3}$ s⁻¹, D_{mix} of 2.26×10^{-9} m² s⁻¹, and H_{mix} of 0.05. These values were obtained by fitting
181 the experimental data to the model prediction, minimizing the sum of the norm between the
182 differences of experimental RE and modeled RE.

183 The mass transfer coefficient obtained here was 19% lower than that in the conventional BTF
184 (K_{La} of styrene in water of 1.14×10^{-2} s⁻¹, Part 1), thus indicating that the addition of silicone
185 oil increased the mass transfer resistance. Dumont et al. (2014) observed that the silicone oil
186 addition slightly hindered the mass transfer rate compared with the air/water system but that

187 this drop would only be apparent, balancing the greater driving force related to the decrease
188 in the partitioning coefficient. Other authors have suggested that the negative effect of a NAP
189 on the mass transfer coefficient could be explained by the viscosity of the NAP or the
190 formation of a rigid film that causes an increase in the mass transfer resistance (Rols and
191 Goma, 1989; Yeom et al., 2010). Several recent studies have revealed that the effect of the
192 NAP on mass transfer coefficients remained unclear regardless of which solute was used or
193 configuration was applied and that no general trends had been established to date (Dumont
194 and Andrès, 2012; Hernández et al., 2011; Quijano et al., 2009a). The direct comparison of
195 the variation in the K_{La} of styrene in water–silicone mixtures versus water is not possible for
196 TPPB-BTF due to the lack of literature data. Using a stirred reactor aerated with air polluted
197 with styrene, Dumont and Andrès (2012) obtained a decrease in the ratio of $K_{La,mix}/K_{La,water}$ of
198 0.37, 0.07, and 0.03 for mixtures of silicone oil of 2%, 10%, and 20%, respectively. These
199 authors concluded that to consider K_{La} a good parameter to characterize the effect of the
200 silicone oil addition in the mass transfer, the partition coefficient value must be consistently
201 expressed in the mass transfer model (H_{water} , H_{NAP} , H_{mix}).

202 The affinity of styrene for silicone oil has been further established in the literature with a
203 well-accepted value of Henry's law constant of styrene in silicone oil (H_{NAP}) of is $4.1 \pm 0.6 \times$
204 10^{-4} , which is approximately 236 times lower than that in water (0.1, Patel et al., 2017). The
205 value of the water–silicone mixture is usually calculated on the basis of the contribution of
206 the percentage of silicone oil and water (Dumont et al., 2010; Hernández et al., 2011; Quijano
207 et al., 2010). In the current study, another approach was used for the first time in which H_{mix}
208 was selected as the calibration parameter for a TPPB-BTF with biomass. It yielded a value of
209 0.05, which was one order of magnitude higher than that predicted by the contribution of the
210 percentage of silicone oil and water according to Henry's law constant of styrene in silicone
211 oil and that in water. The lower increase in the styrene solubility could be attributed to the

212 dynamic associated to the biofilm evolution and to the production of metabolites (i.e., extra-
213 cellular polymeric substances and soluble particulate matter), which could mask, to some
214 extent, the contribution of silicone oil by phenomena such as absorption and/or adsorption.
215 Regarding the third calibration parameter, the value of diffusivity obtained from the water–
216 silicone liquid, D_{mix} , was 2.5 times higher than that in water. Data are lacking related to VOC
217 diffusivity in silicone oil; Dumont et al. (2012) pointed out that the diffusion coefficient of
218 styrene in a silicone oil of five times greater viscosity than water should be around four times
219 higher than that in water according to the general mass transfer enhancement factor model of
220 Zhang et al. (2006), but this was not confirmed experimentally. These authors found that the
221 mass transfer rate in water–silicone oil systems was twice as high as those determined in air–
222 water systems, regardless of the silicone oil volume fraction: 2%, 10%, or 20% or the inlet
223 gas concentration of styrene: 344–1708 mg m⁻³. In our study, with a silicone oil of higher
224 viscosity (50.0 mPa s⁻¹), the proposed value of the diffusivity for the water–silicone emulsion
225 seems to be in line with this prediction. In the present study, the joint calibration of the three
226 parameters that influenced the mass transfer phenomena confirmed the capacity of the tested
227 water–silicone oil mixture to increase the styrene mass transfer by a factor of 1.6.
228 The high correspondence between the model predictions and the experimental data is shown
229 in Fig. 1, which depicts the relationship between the experimental EC and the modeled EC
230 for the three EBRTs tested. The model simulations predicted all the experimental conditions
231 tested, with a maximum relative error of 11%. Statistical analysis of the normalized mean
232 square error demonstrated a goodness of fit of 0.94. Thus, the model application showed that
233 the change in the physical properties of the liquid film from the styrene-degrading BTF
234 model satisfactorily simulated the steady-state performance of the TPPB-BTF at ILs of 13–77
235 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹ and an EBRT of 30–15 s.

236

237 Fig. 1. Comparison between the experimental and the modeled EC of the laboratory TPPB-

238

BTF from model calibration

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240 To compare the TPPB-BTF and the conventional BTF, the EC curve versus IL at an EBRT of

241 15 s along with the model simulation for both systems is shown in Fig. 2. As illustrated, the

242 model predictions reasonably reproduced the ability of the TPPB-BTF to overpass the mass

243 transfer limitation encountered in a conventional BTF for the removal of styrene. Only slight

244 discrepancies of the TPPB model were obtained for the highest tested IL: the model EC

245 prediction was of 38.5 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹ versus the experimental value of 43.2 ± 1.5 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹. By

246 modifying the selected physical properties of the pollutant, the model successfully predicted

247 the improvement in the EC due to the increase in the styrene mass transfer by a factor of 1.6

248 with the NAP addition.

249

250 Fig. 2. Model prediction for the relationship between EC and IL at an EBRT of 15 s: TPPB-
 251 BTF vs. BTF and experimental comparison

252

253 3.2 Sensitivity analysis

254 A sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate the influence of the calibrated parameters on
 255 the model predictions. The analysis was performed using the operational conditions
 256 corresponding to an IL of 43 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹ and an EBRT of 15 s. Model sensitivity was assessed
 257 by varying the selected parameters $\pm 50\%$ and evaluating the effect on the EC, which was
 258 selected as the performance variable. The results are shown in Fig. 3. The sensitivity analysis
 259 revealed that the calibrated parameters were sensitive at the experimental conditions tested.
 260 Moreover, the partition coefficient between gas and the water–silicone mixture was the most
 261 sensitive parameter of the model. The mass transfer and the diffusion coefficients had a
 262 similar influence on the EC, and their sensitivities increased at the low values of the
 263 parameter. For example, a 50% decrease in the $K_{L,mix}$ and D_{mix} led to a reduction of 13% and
 264 8% on the EC, respectively, whereas a 50% increase led to an improvement of 3–4%.

265

266

Fig. 3. Sensitivity analysis for the calibrated parameters of the TPPB-BTF model

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268 3.3 Model validation under transient conditions

269

The model validation was performed by predicting the instantaneous evolution of the outlet

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gas phase of styrene in two case studies using the same TPPB-BTF working at an EBRT of

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15 s. For this purpose, two different inlet concentration patterns were used. The first pattern

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tested involved four cycles of alternating inlet concentrations at $\sim 100\text{--}700\text{ mg C m}^{-3}$, each for

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2 h (Fig. 4a). The second pattern tested comprised three cycles of inlet concentration

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fluctuations of approximately 100, 250, 400, 550, and 350 mg C m^{-3} (Fig. 4b). The model

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predictions, which showed good agreement, are shown in Fig. 4. The slight differences in the

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dynamic between the experimental data and the model predictions in the outlet gas phase

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concentration could be attributed to dynamic phenomena, such as instantaneous absorption

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on the biofilm that is not accounted for in the present model. The model predicted a drastic

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drop in the TPPB-BTF performance from an RE of approximately 80% at an inlet

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concentration of $\sim 100\text{ mg C m}^{-3}$ to a RE of $\sim 20\%$ at an inlet concentration peak of $\sim 700\text{ mg}$

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C m^{-3} (Fig. 4a). The model consistently predicted the dynamic response in the outlet

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concentration when the inlet concentration increased and of the time required to recover the

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nominal conditions when the inlet concentration decreased to approximately 100 mg C m^{-3} .

284

Therefore, the model predictions indicate that under dynamic conditions, the TPPB-BTF

285 could recover the previous high RE after applying a peak of concentration nearly seven times
286 higher than the nominal one. Fig. 4b illustrates the dynamic response of the TPPB-BTF and
287 the model simulation when the second styrene feeding was applied. This figure shows the
288 capability of the model to simulate the variation of the outlet concentration with the RE at
289 80% and 55%, for inlet concentrations of $\sim 100 \text{ mg C m}^{-3}$ and $\sim 350 \text{ mg C m}^{-3}$, respectively.
290 At high inlet concentrations (~ 450 and 550 mg C m^{-3}) the REs dropped up to 40%. This
291 result indicates that the model developed here can be used as a powerful tool for predicting
292 the TPPB-BTF performance under steady and transient conditions. In addition, the response
293 of the treatment system toward unexpected styrene shock loadings can be anticipated through
294 model simulations, allowing the development of operating protocols for pollutant shock
295 loading.

296

297 Fig. 4. Experimental data and model predictions of the TPPB-BTF from variations in the inlet
 298 styrene concentration in the lab-scale TPPB-BTF (EBRT of 15 s).

299

300 3.4 Comparison between TPPB-BTF and conventional BTF

301 The developed models for conventional BTF (Part 1) and TPPB-BTF (Part 2) were used to

302 compare their performance under different operational conditions to demonstrate the

303 applicability and usefulness of the modeling approach and the potential performance

304 improvement caused by adding silicone oil. First, the model from Part 1 was used to predict

305 the response of a styrene-degrading BTF from the literature (Pérez et al., 2015) to show its

306 applicability in a wide range of operational conditions. Then, the TPPB-BTF model was used

307 to estimate the improvement in terms of EC that would have been achieved if silicone oil had
 308 been added.

309 The first scenario corresponds to a BTF treating styrene with an IL of 12–38 g m⁻³ h⁻¹, an
 310 EBRT of 30–60 s and an intermittent irrigation (15 min every 2 h) from Pérez et al. (2015).
 311 The compilation of the experimental data is shown in Table 2. The results from the model
 312 simulation along with the experimental data are depicted in Fig. 5. The high grade of
 313 correspondence (goodness of fit of 0.91) corroborates that the model developed for a styrene-
 314 degrading BTF is valid in the typical range of design and operational parameters. The BTF
 315 treating styrene fully degraded styrene (RE > 90%) at a maximum IL of 15 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹
 316 (EBRT = 60 s). Further increases in the IL by decreasing the EBRT or by increasing the inlet
 317 concentration hindered the RE up until 75%. The model predicted this behavior at an EBRT
 318 of 45–60 s, which was unlike that used for calibration (15–30 s). Thus, the model's suitability
 319 was successfully validated in the wide range of EBRTs of 15–60 s and ILs of 10–77 g C m⁻³
 320 h⁻¹.

321

322 Table 2. Compilation of experimental styrene removal performance from Pérez et al. (2015)

C _{in} (mg Nm ⁻³)	EBRT (s)	C _{out} (mg Nm ⁻³)	RE (%)	IL (g m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)	EC (g m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)
216 ± 14	60	13	94	12	11
290 ± 12	60	29	90	16	14
391 ± 3	60	99 ± 28	75	22	16
444 ± 39	60	109 ± 40	75	24	18
355 ± 50	45	64 ± 10	82	26	21
512 ± 5	45	115 ± 25	78	38	29
180 ± 0	30	45 ± 11	75	20	15

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324

325

326 Fig. 5. Application of the BTF model to simulate the literature data on styrene-degrading

327

BTF (Pérez et al., 2015)

328

329 The TPPB-BTF model was applied to evaluate the potential improvements in the styrene
 330 removal of this BTF. Fig. 6 summarizes the comparison between both models (BTF-Part 1
 331 and the TPPB-BTF). This BTF system was mass transfer limited for the tested ILs and
 332 EBRTs. For all data, the TPPB-BTF model predicted an improvement in the EC, which was
 333 related to the enhancement of the styrene mass transfer in the water–silicone/air system in
 334 comparison with the water/air system. This improvement increased the critical IL; this effect
 335 was more noticeable for shorter EBRTs (45 and 30 s). These results strongly suggested that
 336 using TPPB-BTF for styrene abatement could be recommended in mass transfer limited
 337 systems. The model approach is shown as a valuable tool in the design and operation of
 338 TPPB-BTFs.

339 This is the first attempt to model a TPPB-BTF with biomass operated under typical
 340 conditions found in industrial BTFs. Further investigation on the influence of the percentage
 341 of silicone oil in the sensitivity of the model parameters would expand its applicability.

342

343

344 Fig. 6. Potential improvement in styrene removal by adding silicone oil according to model

345 predictions. Open symbols correspond to BTF and solid symbols to the TPPB-BTF.

346

347 4. Conclusions

348 A dynamic model to simulate TPPB-BTFs was developed, calibrated, and validated by

349 extending the modeling approach used in Part 1 for conventional BTFs. The styrene removal

350 of a laboratory TPPB-BTF was successfully simulated by modifying the physical properties

351 of styrene in the water–silicone liquid mixture, accurately predicting the enhanced outlet

352 performance. Moreover, the model predicted, with a high grade of correspondence, the

353 transient conditions by simulating the peaks of the emissions associated with the high

354 fluctuations in the inlet concentration. Model predictions consistently proved that the

355 presence of silicone oil improved the removal of styrene by BTFs by enhancing diffusion and

356 solubility, although mass transfer resistance increased by 19%. To the best of our knowledge,

357 this work is the first on the mathematical modeling of TPPB-BTFs operated under dynamic

358 conditions according to industrial applications.

359

360

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365

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457 **Nomenclature**

a	Specific surface area of the packing material
C	Concentration
D	Diffusion coefficient
f(X_v)	Correction factor of diffusivity in the biofilm according to Fan's equation
H	Partitioning coefficient
K	Half saturation rate constant of the substrate
K_La	Overall mass transfer coefficient of the substrate
S	Concentration in the biofilm
t	Time
v	Superficial velocity
x	Coordinate for the depth in the biofilm
X_v	Biomass concentration in the biofilm
Y	Yield coefficient
z	Axial coordinate in the reactor from the inlet to the outlet
Greek letters	
β	Thickness of the liquid film
δ	Thickness of the biofilm
θ_B	Volume fraction occupied by the biofilm
θ_G	Porosity of the bioreactor
θ_L	Volume fraction occupied by the liquid film
θ_P	Void space of the packing material
μ_{max}	Maximum specific growth rate of the substrate
Subscripts	
G	Gas
L	Liquid
B	Biofilm
mix	Properties of styrene in the pseudo-homogeneous water–silicone mixture
Sty	Styrene
O	Oxygen

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